

Kaole Mosques

By Akshay Sarathi, Texas A&M University

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The city of Kaole was occupied between the 13th and 16th cen. CE and is located in the Bagamoyo District of the Tanzania. It is located close to the historic site of Bagamoyo. The name of the site, according to local lore, is based on the Zaramo word for "go and see". The site participated in the Indian Ocean trade network, as evidenced by excavated Chinese ceramics and Indian Ocean trade beads. While most of the houses were likely constructed of mud and wood and thus have not survived, a couple of large, presumably elite, non-religious structures have survived. However, one of them has identified by locals as a madrassa. There are two mosques on the site, with associated tombs. A possible mausoleum is located at the site as well. Some of the graves are supposed to be of local rulers known as "Diwanis", believed to be descendants of Sheikh Ali Muhammad al-Hatim al-Barawi. One mosque is more intact than the other. The larger mosque is noteworthy because of its staircase - rather than tower - minaret. The second, collapsed mosque, has a steeply rising mass of stone masonry, presumably the remains of the collapsed turning staircase minaret. The staircase has also been identified as a minbar. The mihrab of this larger mosque is a recessed chamber in which one person can comfortable stand. The ruination of the mosques makes greater description impossible. While archaeological excavations have taken place within the site of Kaole, it is unknown whether any of them specially targeted the mosque. A tree that is supposed to grant years of life for each time it is circumambulated is located near the site.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 1500 CE

Region: Kaole

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Tanzania

The current archaeological site of Kaole

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Schacht, Joseph. "Further notes on the staircase minaret." *Ars Orientalis* (1961): 137-141.

— Source 2: Ichumbaki, Elgidius B. "A history of conservation of built heritage sites of the Swahili Coast in Tanzania." *African Historical Review* 48.2 (2016): 43-67.

– Source 3: Pradines, Stéphane. *Historic Mosques in Sub-Saharan Africa: From Timbuktu to Zanzibar*. Vol. 163. Brill, 2022.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: None

– Source 1 Description: None

– Source 2 URL: None

– Source 2 Description: None

– Source 3 URL: None

– Source 3 Description: None

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: Unknown

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Neville Chittick? Tanzanian Government?

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Water source

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The site is associated with a baobab which adds years to one's life based on how many times it is circumambulated. The site is also located along the shore, and the mosque may have served as lighthouse/marker for vessels nearing the site. Finally, the site is associated with several freshwater wells that may have had ritual significance before the conversion of the people of the site to Islam.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Trackway or road-surface

– Other [specify]: City

Notes: The mosque was part of a city with two mosques. While the majority of the city may have been constructed of perishable materials, there are a few extant stone structures. There are trackways connecting the different parts of the site together, and a main road runs close to the site.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The mosque(s) was located in the heart of the ancient city of Kaole, near the port. The site today lies near the city of Bagamoyo,

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The mosque(s) was located in the heart of the ancient city of Kaole, near the port. The site today lies near the city of Bagamoyo.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: The mosque(s) was located in the heart of the ancient city of Kaole, near the port. The site today lies near the city of Bagamoyo, and today is considered to be in a rural setting.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The site of Kaole is fairly small and the mosque(s) is located within walking distance of the other structures of the site.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: Multiple structures, tombs, and a possible mausoleum are present.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: The mosque is associated with a freshwater well, a port, and baobab tree that adds years to one's life each time it is circumambulated. The baobab may be a later addition.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is part of a larger settlement that contains stone structures, tombs, and a possible mausoleum. There were likely other structures built of perishable materials at the site.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– I don't know

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is associated with a freshwater well, a port, and a baobab that adds years to one's life each time it is circumambulated.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– I don't know

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The two mosques are part of the larger settlement of Kaole.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Both communal and individual Islamic worship

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unknown whether repairs/reconstructions took place for either of the mosques at the site.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: The mosques have collapsed over time, presumably after the site was abandoned.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: The mosques were likely not destroyed purposely.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: The mosques likely collapsed as a result of neglect when the site was abandoned.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The mosques today lie in ruins

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The mosques were dedicated to the Muslim God.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– I don't know

Notes: While the mosques were likely dedicated to only one being - Allah - it is possible that other supernatural beings were associated with the site, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: While the mosques were likely used to worship only Allah, it possible that in the past they were associated with some semi-divine human being, given the idiosyncratic and syncretic nature of East African Islam.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: While the mosques were likely used to worship only Allah, it possible that in the past they were associated with some non-divine ancestors, given the idiosyncratic and syncretic nature of East African Islam.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The people responsible for the construction of the mosque remain unknown, but they likely were the elite of Kaole or some rich merchant participating in Indian Ocean trade.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The people responsible for the construction of the mosque remain unknown, but they likely were the elite of Kaole or some rich merchant participating in Indian Ocean trade.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The site may have been selected as a result of divine intervention. But why the sites was chosen for the construction of the mosques remains unknown.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Kaole or at least the location of its mosques may have been chosen to commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being. Given the idiosyncratic and syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, this is entirely possible.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Kaole or at least the location of its mosques may have been chosen as the result of an event. The field does not have enough information to answer this question.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The construction of the mosques may have been funded by external money, by the elites of Kaole, or by some rich merchant participating in Indian Ocean trade networks.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The mosques at Kaole could have been constructed as an act of thanksgiving to God/gods, with expectation of favor in return, or with no expectation of favor in return. The field does not know.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Presumably, the mosques held copies of the Quran.

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, Qurans were stored in these mosques. However, where in the mosques the Qurans were stored remains unknown.

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, Qurans were stored in these mosques. However, where in the mosques the Qurans were stored remains unknown.

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– Yes

↳ Are they read aloud:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, given current Muslim practice, the Quran was read out loud to a human audience.

↳ To a human audience

– Yes

↳ Are they studied:

– Yes

Notes: A structure identified as a madrassa lies close to the larger mosque. If this identification is correct, the Quran and other texts could have been studied there. This would be in keeping with current practice in which some mosques are places where the Quran is actively studied.

↳ Are they recopied:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The mosques and/or the presumed madrassas could have been sites where the Quran was (re)copied.

↳ Used for divination:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: That sacred texts could have been used for divination purposes is entirely possible, especially given the heterodox practices associated with idiosyncratic and syncretic East African Islam.

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: None

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The mosques (especially the larger mosque) is associated with the port. Both mosques are associated with well.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Notes: But the mosques are part of the urban fabric and are associated with the city. They are associated with built wells.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: One mosque is definitely larger and thus presumably more important than the other mosque.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: No one seems to have mapped the site of Kaole.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: No one has mapped the site properly and measured the mosques.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: No one has measured the height of the mosque.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: No one has measured the mosque

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: No one has measured the mosques.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: The mosques are constructed on an earth base into which their foundations are sunk.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The construction of the mosque presumably involved the use of sand, especially in the making of plaster.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: Beach sand is readily available.

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Clay was likely used in the mortar holding the stones of the mosques together.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: Lime plaster made of burning shell or limestone blocks was used as mortar and to face the mosques.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably, wood was used especially to hold up the now-collapsed roofs of the mosques. I don't know what type of wood was used and thus cannot answer whether it was sourced locally or not.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably, wood was used especially to hold up the now-collapsed roofs of the mosques. I don't know what type of wood was used and thus cannot answer whether it was sourced locally or not. Note that wood in general is available in the local environment now.

↳ Grass

– I don't know

Notes: If grass/fiber was used in the construction of the mosques, it remains unknown.

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Limestone blocks, likely sourced locally, were used in the construction of the mosques.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Plaster produced by burning shells or limestone blocks was used in the construction of the mosque.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– I don't know

Notes: The dilapidated condition of the mosques makes it impossible to discern whether decoration was present on the outside.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The mihran is marked by a decorated niche framed by an arch

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

Notes: Movable reliefs, tapestries, and mats may have been present in the past when the mosque was in use, but they are no longer present.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

Notes: In keeping with Islamic tradition, no figural decoration is present.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: If other types of non-figural decorations were present when the mosque was in use, they are now lost.

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The mihrab is framed by an arch and decorated with some basic geometric motifs

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: The decorated mihrab is visible for all who enter the mosque to see.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: In accordance with accepted Islamic practice, no statues are present currently. Presumably, this was the case in the past.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Geometric reliefs in the mihrab

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Notes: If paintings were present in the past, they are no longer present.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: But there are associated cemeteries with characteristic Swahili pillar tombs and a possibly mausoleum

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: In accordance with standard Islamic practice, the mosques were likely not used to worship the dead. However, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that worship of the dead took place. This is unknown however.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque has not been in use for a few centuries, so it is unknown if it was used to treat bodies that were subsequently deposited in the associated cemeteries.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the

tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: But it should be noted that many of the tombs have recesses within which imported ceramics would have been attached

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: But it should be noted that many of the tombs have recesses within which imported ceramics would have been attached

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: There do seem to be monuments to/tombs of special individuals and a possible mausoleum. According to local tradition, some of the tombs are the graves of local rulers who were known as "diwanis". "Diwanis" are believed to be the descendants of the Sheikh Ali Muhamad al-Hatim al-Barawi.

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are associated cemeteries with the mosques. According to local tradition, some of the tombs are the graves of local rulers who were known as "diwanis". "Diwanis" are believed to be the descendants of the Sheikh Ali Muhamad al-Hatim al-Barawi.

Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: There is a possible mausoleum associated with the mosques. According to local tradition, some of the tombs are the graves of local rulers who were known as "diwanis". "Diwanis" are believed to be the descendants of the Sheikh Ali Muhamad al-Hatim al-Barawi.

Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– I don't know

Notes: The burials seem to be only in the cemetery associated with the mosques, but it is possible that burials took place in domestic contexts as well.

Other

– Other [specify]: None

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

Notes: Allah is often described in anthropomorphic terms and has human-like qualities, but Muslims are prevented from creating or possessing any image of Allah.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– I don't know

Notes: Allah could be considered a sky deity according to some traditions.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Notes: However, it is possible that the rulers of the site drew legitimacy from their connections to the Prophet.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the

elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Allah generally communicates with humans through inspiration, His prophets, and the Quran. However, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that Allah was considered to communicate with the living at this site.

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that previously human spirits are considered to be present.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that previously human spirits were considered to be present and communicated with the living at this site.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that nonhuman supernatural beings were considered present at this site.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that nonhuman supernatural beings were considered to communicate with the living at this place.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that mixed human-divine beings were present, but is against Islamic theology.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that mixed human-divine beings were present and communicated with the living at this site, but is against Islamic theology.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Not at present, and given Islam's strictures against figural depictions of God, it is unlikely that statues to Allah were kept in the mosque.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: The extent to which supernatural monitoring was present at this site is unknown. Given Islamic belief, it is entirely possible that much supernatural monitoring of human behavior took place here. However, the degree to which this was the case in the past is unknown.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that people communicated with God or other supernatural beings at this site. However, this cannot be now known as the site has been abandoned for centuries.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, the rituals were Islamic, but given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is possible that Islam-adjacent rituals took place at the mosque as well.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale Muslim rituals likely took place at the mosques.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Small-scale/individual rituals likely took place in association with the mosques.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: The larger mosque can hold up to 200 people and the smaller perhaps a 100

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Given prevalent Islamic practice, the rituals would have taken place at least five times a day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– I don't know

Notes: Given how long ago the site was abandoned and how syncretic and idiosyncratic East African Islam can be, it is difficult to know for sure whether orthodoxy checks took place and, if they did, whether they were successful.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– I don't know

Notes: Given how long ago the site was abandoned and how syncretic and idiosyncratic East African Islam can be, it is difficult to know for sure whether orthopraxy checks took place and, if they did, whether they were successful.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– I don't know

Notes: Presumably synchronic practices (especially worship) took place in accordance with Islamic teachings. However, the extent to which these were practiced remains unknown.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– I don't know

Notes: According to Islamic teachings, they should not be used. However, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is possible that Islam-adjacent rituals in which intoxicants and mind-altering substances played a role took place.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The degree to which sacrifices were performed at the mosque is unknown, especially given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Notes: According to Islamic practice, self-sacrifices are not permitted. However, whether or not they

took place at the site when it was occupied remains unknown because of syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam.

Are material offerings present:

– No

Notes: But note the Chinese ceramics attached to the tombs at the site.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably, the pressure to attend worship five times a day according to Islamic practice was present at the site. How strictly this was followed and whether people worshipped spirits/ancestors elsewhere is also unknown.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Notes: The site is no long ritually maintained, but it presumably was when it was in use. However, the current maintenance of Kaole as an archaeological site is undertaken by the Tanzanian government.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether people undertook pilgrimages to visit the mosques at Kaole is unknown.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether people feasted in association with the mosques at Kaole is unknown. However, given current theories about medieval Swahili practice and Islamic practices of feasting during holy days, it is entirely possible that feasting took place.

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably, festivals took place in accordance with the Muslim calendar. However, the exact nature of these festivals remains unknown because of the lack of texts associated with the site.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam and given current practice

on the East African coast, it is entirely possible that divination was present at the site when it was occupied.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam and given current practice on the East African coast, it is entirely possible that healing practices were present at the site when it was occupied.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably religious specialists like Imams were associated with the mosques. However, it is unknown whether they were present full time or part time.

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably religious specialists like Imams were associated with the mosques. However, it is unknown whether they were present full time or part time.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– I don't know

Notes: According to Islamic practice, religious specialists are supposed to be male. However, given the syncretic and idiosyncratic nature of East African Islam, it is entirely possible that non-male religious specialists were somehow associated with the mosques.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

Notes: The ethnicity of the religious specialists associated with Kaole's mosques, or if there was a requirement that they be of a specific ethnicity, remains unknown because the site was abandoned so long ago and there are no texts describing religious practice at the site.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

Notes: The class/caste of the religious specialists associated with Kaole's mosques, or if there was a requirement that they be of a specific class/caste, remains unknown because the site was abandoned so long ago and there are no texts describing religious practice at the site.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether the religious specialists associated with the mosques were dedicated to the place for life remains unknown because the site was abandoned so long ago and there are no texts describing religious practice at Kaole.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether the religious specialists associated with the mosques were organized hierarchically remains unknown because the site was abandoned so long ago and there are no texts describing religious practice at Kaole.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: There may have been living spaces for religious specialists associated with the mosques, but they cannot be discerned on the ground at present because of the abandonment and ruination of the mosque.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: But there is a structure close by the largest mosque that has been identified as a madrasa. Whether this identification is correct or not is unknown because of the abandonment and ruination of the site and the lack of texts associated with the site.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Currently, Kaole is maintained by the Tanzanian government as a heritage zone and an archaeological site. It is no longer maintained as a religious site.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Notes: A formal bureaucracy associated with the mosques may have been present when the site was occupied. But whether this was the case is unknown because the site was abandoned centuries ago and there are no texts associated with the site.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Notes: The mosques may have controlled economic resources when the site was occupied. But whether this was the case is unknown because the site was abandoned centuries ago and there are no texts associated with the site.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Notes: The lack of texts from the time Kaole was occupied makes it difficult to know what services the mosques provided to the local community. Presumably, the mosques provided at least religious services to the Kaole community.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: No non-religious writing has been recovered from the mosques. However, it is possible that non-religious writing was stored in the mosques when they were operational. This is unknowable at present.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: Copies of the Quran would have presumably been stored at the mosques.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

Notes: If there was such a story, it has been lost.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: When Kaole was still occupied, the scriptures would have presumably have been interpreted by trained religious specialists.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Kaole Mosques, Joseph, Schacht. "Further Notes on the Staircase Minaret", 1961.

Reference: Kaole Mosques, Lwoga, Noel Biseko. "Heritage Proximity, Attitudes to Tourism Impacts and Residents' Support for Heritage Tourism in Kaole Site, Tanzania" 42, no. 42 (December 1, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.2478/bog-2018-0037>.